

USE OF WEBSITES IN INTERNET MARKETING

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***Аннотация.** в современных условиях количество пользователей сети Интернет увеличивается с каждым днем и предпринимателям необходимо выйти на площадку интернет-маркетинга. Сайт является основным средством коммуникации компании с целевой аудиторией в сети Интернет. Современная веб-разработка предполагает решение нескольких задач: простая навигация, открытый интерфейс, высокий уровень восприятия информации. Сайт отражает индивидуальность компании, создает эффект присутствия и непосредственного взаимодействия с ней. Компания без сайта — это как бизнесмен без визитки. Основой существования и развития любого сайта должна быть определенная бизнес-модель. В данной статье рассматриваются преимущества использования веб-сайта в интернет-маркетинге, его основные функции и характеристики.*

***Ключевые слова:** веб-сайт, интернет-маркетинг, бизнес-модель, навигация, разработка, сеть, интернет, интерфейс, информации, идентификация.*

***Abstract.** in modern conditions, the number of Internet users is increasing every day and entrepreneurs need to enter the Internet marketing platform. The website is the main means of communication of the company with the target audience on the Internet. Modern web development involves solving several problems: simple navigation, open interface, high level of information perception. The website reflects the individuality of the company, creates the effect of presence and direct interaction with it. A company without a website is like a business man without a business card. The basis for the existence and development of any website should be a certain business model. This article discusses the benefits of using a website in online marketing, its main functions and characteristics.*

***Keywords:** website, Internet marketing, business model, navigation, development, network, Internet, interface, information, identification.*

A website is the main means of interaction between a company and its target audience on the Internet. Modern web development involves solving a number of problems: ease of navigation, open interface, high level of information perception. A website is the most common form of online representation of a company.

The site is the main means of communication of the company with the target audience on the Internet. Modern web development involves the solution of several tasks: simple navigation, open interface, high level of perception of information. A website is the most common form of online representation of a company.

These benefits include:

1. increase company productivity;
2. use an additional method of selling goods and services;
3. direct access to the buyer;
4. business improvement;
5. improving relationships with clients;

6. access to additional market niches;
7. fast method of collecting statistical data.

A company's website is its intangible asset, its representation on the Internet.

The website reflects the company's identity, creates the effect of presence and direct interaction with it. A company without a website is like a businessman without a business card. The basis for the existence and development of any website must be a certain business model.

Visiting a company's website gives the effect very close to actually visiting the company, and it's much easier and faster. The website also enables the customer to make a decision to purchase the product in a convenient and unhurried manner.

A corporate website is the primary way of doing business for companies that conduct their business on the Internet. Websites can come in completely different shapes, sizes and forms, but they can still be classified. The main classification factor is functionality. The most important decision a company faces now is what functions the website should perform. The main functions of websites are: business advertising, customer service, public relations, sales support and e-commerce.

The site divides all marketing communication tools into active and passive. Active marketing communications include email advertising, contextual advertising, banner advertising and passive. Passive ones include registration of websites in search engines and directories, exchange of links, electronic PR communications.

Active communications are more valuable than passive ones because they allow you to attract more users to the website in less time, so they need to be used less often. Passive marketing communications are cheaper and should therefore be used regularly.

Photo. 1. Basic functions of a commercial company website.

Photo 1 shows the basic functions of a commercial company website. A company's website is one of the main communicative marketing tools on the Internet, but it can be used to implement the entire marketing complex, along with shaping the flow of communicative information. The company's customers are not the only audience for the site, but they are the only one. Through the website, the company can interact with partners, shareholders, media and other communication audiences.

The main characteristics of the site are characterized by the "7C" model, which includes the following elements:

1. Context as a balance between the aesthetic and functional content of the site, its design and design.
2. Content: images, text, sound and video.
3. Community: ways users can connect with other customers of the company.
4. The ability of the site to implement communication or two-way communication with the company's client.
5. Communication as the level of interaction of a particular site with other sites through placement of links, affiliate programs, search engine optimization.
6. Commerce as a corporate website's capabilities for conducting commercial transactions. For example, storing information about customer registration options, preferences, customer contacts, order delivery options.
7. Customization, personalization of the order by providing information and additional opportunities to different groups of consumers.

A commercial company, both in the consumer sector and in the production sector, can simultaneously implement several communication tools on its website: describe its products and development strategy, sell on the Internet, help its customers in choosing goods and services, provide location information. close seller and others.

Therefore, the impact of a website on its target audience cannot be underestimated. The characteristics of a site that are particularly important for achieving the goals of creating an image and increasing sales can vary greatly. These differences apply to both consumer and industrial markets.

A company's website opens up new opportunities for it to create, build and manage customer relationships. It can be used to move potential buyers from the category of potential customers to the category of actual customers through specific stages of the order creation and purchase process. A website is a great online platform for generating sales.

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